
GLOBAL UNEMPLOYMENT TRENDS AND THE ECONOMIC AND LEGAL CHALLENGES OF GEORGIA'S LABOR MARKET

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Abstract

In the contemporary world, unemployment remains one of the most pressing issues in both developing and developed countries. Unemployment leads to reduced incomes, poverty, increased crime, rising labor migration, higher inflation rates, and a worsening demographic situation. It poses a threat to a country's social and political stability, increases social risks, and limits national competitiveness.

The article examines global trends in unemployment, its socio-economic consequences, and the issues of unemployment and employment in Georgia. Based on quantitative and statistical research methods, the study examines the primary challenges facing Georgia's labor market and the key legislation governing labor relations. Recommendations are provided for reducing unemployment and improving employment indicators, including enhancing labor force competitiveness and further developing human capital, as well as the formation of a digital labor market that ensures the optimal realization of interests among labor market participants and provides dignified and effective employment opportunities for the country's population.

Keywords: Global Unemployment, Poverty, Labor Migration, Labor Market, Labor Code, Georgia.

Introduction. In Georgia's economy, the formation of an efficiently functioning labor market holds particular importance; reducing unemployment and, consequently, increasing employment is a key priority of the country's economic policy. To develop and implement effective labor policies, a thorough analysis of the labor market and the improvement of labor-regulating legislation are essential.

This study aims to identify the main trends and ongoing changes in global and local labor markets, examine the regulatory legislation governing Georgia's labor market, and develop measures that promote the effective employment of the country's population.

Research methodology. The study is based on a review of scientific publications, labor legislation, and statistical data. Both quantitative and qualitative analysis methods were employed in the research process.

Unemployment and Economic Growth. The efficiency of a country's labor market, along with employment and unemployment challenges, is directly proportional to the pace of economic growth. The economic and social prospects of the contemporary world remain uncertain due to geopolitical conflicts, rising

costs of climate change, inflation, and unresolved sovereign debt risks. The resilience of countries' labor markets faces significant challenges. Although the global economy continues to expand at a moderate pace, forecast indicators suggest that its growth rate is gradually slowing, complicating the full recovery of labor markets. In 2024, economic growth reached 3.2 percent, which is lower compared to 3.3 percent in 2023 and 3.6 percent in 2022 [1]. Global growth is projected at 3.0 percent for 2025 and 3.1 percent in 2026, an upward revision from the April 2025 World Economic Outlook [2].

The International Labour Organization (ILO) provides significant information on global unemployment trends. The WESO 2025 report presents an analysis of global labor market trends, highlighting issues related to the slowing of economic recovery, persistent youth unemployment, and gender inequality. According to the ILO report, although overall unemployment remained stable at 4.9 percent in 2024, youth unemployment was significantly higher. Last year, the unemployment rate for young men was 12.4 percent, while for young women it was 12.3 percent [3].

Chart 1

Source: ILOSTAT

Youth unemployment remains highest in upper-middle-income countries, where 16% of young people are unemployed. In low-income countries, this figure is below 8%, although often due to underemployment and informal work. Globally, 12% of young people are still

seeking better prospects, highlighting the need for targeted measures to support young workers [3].

The global disparity in employment between women and men remains significant. The international jobs gap refers to the percentage of the total population that wants to work but is unemployed.

Chart 2

Source: ILOSTAT

Although global unemployment remains stable, real wage growth in 2024 was recorded in only a few developed economies, where labor demand is particularly high. In most countries, real wages have not compensated for the losses incurred during the pandemic and the subsequent period of inflation. One of the reasons for weak real wage growth over the past decade has been the shift of labor market power toward employers.

On the back of stable unemployment rates, the global jobs gap (ILO's summary estimate for the over-

all number of jobs missing) stood at around 402.4 million in 2024. The jobs gap includes about 186 million who are unemployed, 137 million who are part of the potential labour force, mainly discouraged workers, and around 79 million who would like to work but have obligations, such as care, that hinder them from taking up employment.

Unemployment and Poverty. Unemployment, in turn, affects poverty levels. Over the past three decades, the share of workers living in extreme poverty (earning less than \$2.15 per day) has significantly decreased, reflecting global progress in improving living standards.

Evolution of Working Poverty Between 1994 and 2024

Source: ILOSTAT

Currently, more workers earn more than \$3.65 per day, indicating a positive shift in income distribution. However, this progress remains uneven, and extreme poverty will persist in 2025, particularly in low-income regions. Working poverty, while improving globally, continues to affect low-income countries; extreme forms of working poverty impact 240 million workers, or 7 percent of the global workforce. More than half of the international workforce is not adequately covered by social security schemes, legal protection, or workplace safety measures. Inequality has increased [3].

Unemployment and Migration. Rising unemployment and its associated migration processes represent one of the most pressing global challenges of our time. The increase in unemployment is directly linked to the intensification of migration flows. According to the International Organization for Migration (IOM), international migration maintained an upward trajectory in 2024, with the global migrant population surpassing a record 304 million. At the same time, more than 83 million people were forcibly displaced due to conflicts, climate change, and economic instability [4].

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development recognizes that migration is a powerful driver of sustainable development for migrants and their communities. It brings significant benefits in the form of skills, strengthening the labor force, investment, and cultural diversity, and contributes to improving the lives of communities in their countries of origin through skills and financial resources transfer [5].

In Georgia, as in other countries, the factors driving emigration and immigration are complex and related to economic, social, and political changes, as well as individual decisions. Difficult economic conditions, low-paid work, and unemployment contribute to mass migration. To mitigate migration-related risks, it is necessary to expand opportunities for legal labor migration, share best practices from developed countries, and improve the legislative framework [6].

Discussion/Results. After reviewing the global challenges associated with unemployment, the need for

research into state labor policy and the improvement of labor relations legal regulation becomes even more pronounced. To mitigate unemployment-related challenges, it is essential to conduct an in-depth analysis of the labor market and study trends in employment and unemployment, including sectoral, age, gender, and regional dimensions.

Labor statistics in Georgia are compiled by the National Statistics Office (Geostat), which follows the methodology of the International Labour Organization (ILO). The unemployment rate is calculated as the ratio of unemployed persons to the economically active population (labor force). The labor force includes both employed individuals and unemployed persons actively seeking work. According to Geostat methodology, a person who is unemployed but not actively seeking employment (i.e., did not look for work in the four weeks prior to the survey) is considered outside the labor force and is not classified as unemployed. Therefore, in certain cases, the unemployment rate may technically decrease due to a reduction in the labor force without any actual increase in employment. Accordingly, to accurately assess unemployment levels in the country, both labor force and employment parameters must be analyzed.

High unemployment has been one of the primary challenges of Georgia's labor market for many years. However, it is notable that, in recent years, the unemployment rate has shown a declining trend. According to labor market statistics, 2023 was a significant year for Georgia's labor market, as historically low unemployment levels were recorded alongside increases in employment indicators and the average monthly wage of employed persons. In 2023, the unemployment rate was 16.4%, a decrease of 1 percentage point compared to the previous year. The number of unemployed also declined by 2.3% in 2023, totaling 261.7 thousand people. This declining trend continued in subsequent years. According to the National Statistics Office of Georgia, the unemployment rate fell to 13.9% in 2024 and was recorded at 14.7% in the first quarter of 2025 [7].

Table 1

Unemployment Rate and Number of Unemployed

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025-I
Labour force , thousand persons	1523.7	1533.6	1551.6	1596.3	1629.5	1633.6
Employed , thousand persons	1241.8	1217.4	1283.7	1334.6	1402.5	1394.2
Unemployed , thousand persons	281.9	316.2	267.9	261.7	227.0	239.4
Unemployment rate , percentage	18.5	20.6	17.3	16.4	13.9	14.7

Source: <https://www.geostat.ge/>

In recent years, although the working-age population and labor force participation have declined due to low natural growth and increased migration flows, the growth of the economically active population and participation rate is evident. Specifically, in 2023, compared to the same period of the previous year, the economically active population increased by 2.9%, reaching 1,596.3 thousand people. Additionally, the participation rate rose by 1.4 percentage points to 53.3% [8].

Chart 4

Economically Active Population: Size and Rate

Source: <https://www.lmis.gov.ge/>

The unemployment rate among men exceeds that of women. One of the contributing factors is the unequal participation of men and women in the labor force (men – 65.1%, women – 43.1%). In 2023, compared to the previous year, unemployment decreased for both women and men. Specifically, in 2023, the unemployment rate for women was 14% (97 thousand unemployed), representing a 0.6 percentage point decrease compared to the same period of the previous year, while for men, the unemployment rate was 18.3% (164.8 thousand unemployed), reflecting a one percentage point decrease compared to the previous year [8].

Source: <https://www.lmis.gov.ge/>

One of the main challenges of the labor market remains the high unemployment rate among young people. That is primarily due to the fact that young people mainly acquire higher education and, upon graduation, face the reality that, on one hand, there is limited demand in the labor market for the professions they have trained in; on the other hand, their qualifications and work experience do not meet labor market requirements. It should also be noted that, for various reasons, young people need more time to find a desired job. Considering all of this, it is particularly noteworthy that the most significant decrease in the unemployment rate was observed in the 20–24 age group, with a reduction of 5.4 percentage points compared to the same period of the previous year [8].

Chart 6

Source: <https://www.lmis.gov.ge/>

The trend of decreasing unemployment is observed in both urban and rural areas. In 2023, the unemployment rate in rural areas was 14.6%, decreasing to 13.3% in 2024. In urban areas, unemployment was 17.6% in 2023 and 14.4% in 2024. Uneven distribution of economic activity and foreign direct investment across Georgia's regions affects internal migration, with labor mobility primarily directed toward the capital. The high concentration of the labor force in Tbilisi, in turn, contributes to a higher unemployment rate.

Regarding employment, as of September 1, 2024, the number of employed persons was 862,731, 3% higher compared to the same period of the previous year. Of these, 92% were employed full-time, while 8% part-time. The majority of employed individuals work in the non-governmental sector. In 2023, the share of employment in the non-governmental sector was 75%.

Chart 7

Source: <https://www.lmis.gov.ge/>

By type of economic activity, the most prominent sector in the employment structure is agriculture, accounting for 16.5% of total employment. Employment levels have increased across almost all types of economic activity. Notably, the information and communications sector, the accommodation and food services sector, and the construction and industry sectors stand out. According to 2023 data, the number of employed persons decreased in only three sectors: agriculture by 3.7%, by 3.2% in other service activities, and a 2.8% decline in the arts, entertainment, and recreation sector.

Research confirms that the primary source of employment in Georgia's labor market is the business sector. Depending on planned projects, ongoing work in various sectors, and expected technological changes, new directions and professions may emerge, generating increased demand in the near future. Specifically, such sectors and professions may arise in energy (energy efficiency and renewable energy), telecommunications, transportation and logistics, water supply and environmental protection, and agriculture [8].

To address the mismatch between labor supply and demand, the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia conducted a 2025 survey on enterprise demand for human capital skills. According to the study, based on educational attainment, 57% of employees have higher education, 27% have secondary education, and the lowest share, 16% have vocational education. The survey assessed employees' skills according to the following criteria: technical skills, quality control skills, problem-solving skills, teamwork and collaboration skills, efficient production skills, safety skills, adaptability and flexibility, time management and organizational skills, communication skills, and leadership skills [9]. The study revealed that employees' skills primarily require development. Both the education system and enterprises themselves need to be involved in this process. Developing human capital skills will help balance labor market supply and demand.

In recent years, Georgia has experienced a negative migration balance, which negatively affects both labor force participation and employment levels. The growth of international migration in Georgia has been facilitated by the accelerated visa liberalization process with the European Union and better opportunities for employment and education in developed countries. Georgian citizens enjoy visa-free travel to 72 countries, allowing for free movement. Establishing a system to manage migration processes requires attention to Georgia's 2021–2030 Migration Strategy, which defines the country's long-term vision for key migration directions while placing greater demands on the implementation process, its mechanisms, and the involved institutions [10].

Labor migration in Georgia is regulated by the Law of Georgia "On Labor Migration" [11], which has been in force since November 1, 2015. The law governs the employment of Georgian citizens abroad, the status and responsibilities of employment agencies, and establishes mechanisms to protect the rights of Georgian citizens working overseas. In 2015, by government decree (#417), the Government of Georgia also approved regulations on the employment of foreigners in Georgia, which are gradually being updated and refined.

The positive effects of labor emigration can be enhanced through the development of circular labor migration schemes. These schemes help to regulate migration flows within a legal framework, align the interests of both the sending and receiving countries, as well as the migrants themselves, and, significantly, facilitate their return to Georgia. Circular migration improves the economic opportunities, professional skills, and migration experience of Georgian citizens. Well-managed circular labor migration ensures increased protection of migrant workers' rights and helps mitigate unemployment issues within the country [6].

The primary legislative act regulating labor relations in Georgia is the Labor Code of Georgia. The fundamental principles of labor law are also reflected in the Constitution of Georgia. The country strives for further alignment with European and international labor standards and practices [12].

Labor law, at its core, is critical to the establishment of a democratic state. It defines minimum protection measures that provide employees with a positive legal standing in the labor market [13].

Protecting the interests of employers and employees, creating equal opportunities for self-realization for every citizen, and safeguarding labor rights are essential challenges for Georgia. According to Article 26 of the Constitution of Georgia, freedom of labor is guaranteed [14]. Everyone has the right to freely choose their work and safe working conditions. The study of labor rights starts with the individual, while the foundation for labor relations is created by the legal state. The primary task of labor law is to establish an efficiently functioning labor market, enabling the rational allocation of labor, a vital resource, across firms, sectors, professions, and regions [15].

Labor relations arise on the basis of equality between the parties (Article 2.2 of the Labor Code of Georgia) [16]; however, the contractual terms are determined by the employer. According to the law, before entering into a contract, the employee must be provided with information about the work to be performed, the form (oral or written) and duration (fixed or indefinite) of the employment contract, working conditions, the employee's legal status during the employment relationship, and remuneration. That ensures that the employee's qualifications and skills correspond to the employment conditions. After the contract is concluded, the employer is responsible for creating an equal and safe working environment for employees (Articles 11, 12, 13, 14, and other provisions of the Labor Code of Georgia) [17].

Under conditions of globalization and the digital transformation of the economy, the nature and content of social-labor relations and work itself are fundamentally changing. New non-standard forms of employment are emerging, and processes of labor universalization and intellectualization are strengthening. For the future workforce, the most in-demand skills include creative and analytical thinking, technological literacy, systems thinking, expertise in artificial intelligence (AI) and big data, as well as competencies related to management, leadership, and cybersecurity [18].

Although digital work platforms currently do not play a significant role in employment, their importance is expected to grow in the future. The extent of their impact on employment prospects will depend on Georgia's level of technological development and education [19].

With the rapid rise of new digital technologies, Georgia is seeking to leverage the potential of artificial intelligence, which creates new opportunities for decent jobs. "Several changes have been introduced into the Labor Code of Georgia, legally regulating labor relations, which constitutes an important prerequisite for the development of the labor market" [12].

Conclusion and Recommendations. Considering the high unemployment rate and inefficient employment in Georgia, improving the labor market requires a thorough analysis of its current state, studying trends in labor market demand, and identifying existing challenges. Particularly significant is the development

of online employment platforms and aligning the workforce with labor market needs, focusing on knowledge, skills, and qualifications.

A key prerequisite for the development of Georgia's labor market is the improvement of the Labor Code of Georgia, through legislative changes that ensure strong guarantees for employees' rights and the establishment and strengthening of effective institutions for labor rights protection, as well as alignment with international labor law. Raising public awareness of labor rights will enhance legal consciousness, protect the rights of both employees and employers, integrate labor resources into economic processes, and foster labor market development.

To reduce unemployment and improve employment indicators in Georgia, the following measures are recommended:

- **Development of human capital** – Strengthening the education and vocational training system and cultivating modern labor skills;
- **Development of the digital labor market** – Integrating online employment platforms and labor databases to increase labor market transparency;
- **Support for small and medium-sized enterprises** – Using investment and tax incentives to create new jobs;
- **Promotion of regional employment** – Developing infrastructure projects and creating job opportunities in regions to reduce migration;
- **Management of labor migration** – Strengthening legal migration mechanisms and facilitating the return of skilled personnel;
- **Strengthening social dialogue** – Active cooperation among the state, employers, and trade unions in shaping employment policy.

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